

Research Article

Criterion physical fitness components relation with ball badminton player's performance

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was criterion performance physical fitness components relation with ball badminton performance. The 150 male ball badminton players were selected inter-university representation in the academic year of 2016–2017, 2017–2018, 2018–2019, and 2019–2020 in Andhra Pradesh State on non-randomly by purposive sample which was used. Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation was used to analysis of the collected data on criterion performance physical fitness components were simple reaction ability (0.528*), aerobic endurance (0.423*), muscular endurance (0.291*), agility (0.328*), orientation ability (0.515*), dynamic balance (0.333*), and dynamic flexibility (0.369*) coefficient of correlation with ball badminton performance which had been positively with significant level 0.05. Remaining performance physical fitness components did not correlate on this current study.

Keywords: Ball badminton players, Performance, Physical fitness components

INTRODUCTION

Ball badminton originated in Tanjore in Tamil Nadu. It became popular, commanding the interest of the Maharaja of Tanjore. The game attracted many players from southern India and is about as well-known as cricket in that part of the country. Previously, ball badminton was an attractive game for rural boys since it required a minimum of equipment. The game drew a large number of students from South India, resulting in the formation of the Ball Badminton Federation of India in 1954. Ball badminton eventually spread to Andhra Pradesh, and the first national championship was conducted at Hyderabad in 1956. It was later introduced at the Junior and Sub-Junior levels.

Ball badminton is an indigenous sport of India. It is a racquet game played with a woolen ball on a court of fixed dimensions by two teams of five players's each. This also played by two players called Doubles and by only one player each side called singles. This game was played as early as 1856 by the royal

family in Tanjore, Capital of Thanjavur district in Tamil Nadu, India. The game is widely prevalent in India and will strike someone new to it as a mixture between volleyball, badminton, and tennis. The game attained popularity in the river basins of Cauvery, Krishna, and Godavari. It is an exceedingly fast game demanding skill, quick perception, correct judgment, agility of movement, and capacity to control the ball with proper movement of wrist. Fitness is the ability to meet the demands of a physical task. Basic fitness can be classified in four main components: Strength, speed, stamina, and flexibility. However, exercise scientists have identified nine components that comprise the definition of fitness: Strength, power, agility, balance, flexibility, local muscle endurance, strength endurance, and co-ordination. All the nine elements of fitness cardiac respiratory qualities are the most important to develop as they enhance all the other components of the conditioning equation. Boxing is combative of applied athletics and it requires well proportionate physique and great amount of physical fitness level. Training components generally classified two categories, one is health related physical fitness components and skill-related training components, in which both were so much useful for making healthful wellbeing and develop of specific game/sport fitness bodies players, but specific or performance training components may would be

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Table 1: Performance physical fitness components

S. No	Performance physical fitness components	Test
1	Complex reaction ability	Nelson reaction test
2*	Simple reaction ability	Nelson reaction test
3*	Aerobic endurance	1 Mile run test
4	Speed endurance	300 M run
5*	Muscular endurance	Push-ups
6*	Agility	Shuttle run
7*	Orientation ability	Baseball throw
8	Explosive strength	Standing broad jump
9*	Dynamic balance	Balance test
10*	Dynamic flexibility	Flexibility test
11	Anaerobic endurance	Margaria-Kalamen test
13	Endurance	600 Yard run
14	Static flexibility	Sit and reach test
15	Maximum Strength	1rm Test

Table 2: Criterion performance physical fitness components association with ball badminton performance

S. No	Performance Physical Fitness Components	Coefficient of Correlation "r"
1	Complex Reaction Ability	0.187
2	Simple Reaction ability	0.528*
3	Aerobic endurance	0.423*
4	Speed endurance	0.231
5	Muscular endurance	0.291*
6	Agility	0.328*
7	Orientation ability	0.515*
8	Explosive strength	0.199
9	Dynamic balance	0.333*
10	Dynamic flexibility	0.369*
11	Anaerobic endurance	0.219
13	Endurance	0.197
14	Static flexibility	0.213
15	Maximum strength	0.193

n=150, r. 05 (150)=0.238, *Significant at 0.05 level

developed good conditioning of fitness body and to perform top performance in a specific competition.

METHODOLOGY

Purpose of the Study

This study would be decided the criterion performance physical fitness components relation with ball badminton performance.

Figure 1: Criterion performance physical fitness components relation with ball badminton performance

Selection of the Subjects

One hundred and fifty male ball badminton players were selected who had been inter-university representation in the academic year of 2016–2017, 2017–2018, 2018–2019, and 2019–2020 in Andhra Pradesh State on non-randomly by purposive sample which had been used.

Collection of the Data and Tools

The data have been collected by administrating the standard procedures for taking performance physical fitness components as well as ball badminton player's performance and tools were used stop watches, push-up stands, and flexible measuring tape for flexibility. The score has been recorded time in the nearest one tenth of the seconds and nearest centimeters.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

To find out the relationship of criterion performance physical fitness components with ball badminton player's performance with the Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation had been used and testing the hypothesis, the level of confidence is 0.05.

An analysis of the above table reveals that ball badminton players had been significantly related to criterion performance physical fitness components were simple reaction ability (0.528*), aerobic endurance (0.423*), muscular endurance (0.291*), agility (0.328*), orientation ability (0.515*), dynamic balance (0.333*), and dynamic flexibility (0.369*) as obtained values of correlation were greater than $r = 0.238$ the correlation to be significant at 0.05 performance physical fitness components were explosive strength, anaerobic endurance, endurance, maximum strength, static flexibility, complex reaction ability, and speed endurance as their correlation values are less than $r = 0.238$ need for significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

As for the results finally, the study exposes that ball badminton performance would be significantly related to criterion performance physical fitness components were simple reaction ability (0.528*), aerobic endurance (0.423*), muscular endurance (0.291*), agility (0.328*), orientation ability (0.515*), dynamic balance (0.333*), and dynamic flexibility (0.369*) as per the analysis, suggested that to the coaches, physical directors, physical education teachers, and physical instructors to concentrate on the above criterion performance physical fitness components while selecting or screening for ball badminton players in a basic level. It would be given effective and good performance in a specific competition.

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